

FORMATION OF MODERN AMERICAN POETRY

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Annotation: This thesis aims to explore and analyze formation of American Poetry, examining the key elements and techniques of Walt Whitman employed that revolutionized the free verse in American Poetry.

Key words: Walt Whitman, modern American poetry, national literature, poetic tradition, form of verse, French vers libre.

Each nation has brought something of its own to world literature, which is revealed not only through a description of the mentality and historical development of the country. Sometimes it is a matter of tradition and attitude to art, sometimes it is a specific range of topics, an appeal to one form from the many offered by culture. The most iconic element that forms the basis of identity is the optics through which a person sees the surrounding reality. Of course, the main load here falls on the national language in which people exist, through which they learn the world and themselves.

When comparing the culture of Europe and America, it may seem that from an aesthetic point of view, the latter is much inferior to the former. European art is rooted in antiquity, American (national) - in the XIX century. But do not rush to conclusions and consider American literature not yet strong. Of course, many American poets and writers were familiar with the latest achievements of European literature and focused on them in their work. But there was another approach, aimed at addressing the actual national roots. The writers who followed him set themselves other tasks, in their own way responded to the cultural challenges common to all nations.

Therefore, the American poetic tradition can be divided into two major branches. The first transferred the principles of European art to its soil in order to rethink it in a new way (Edgar Allan Poe, Emily Dickinson, Robert Frost, Ezra Pound and others, including the expatriate T. S. Eliot), the second preferred to develop an as yet unexplored space. We will consider the second branch - national American poetry - and trace its development from its birth in the 19th century to the present day.

American poetry originated as an attempt to create voices for poetry in the 18th century, before the constitutional unification of the thirteen colonies was decided. Although before this association, oral culture was common among the

Indians. Interestingly, many of the early colonists drew on modern British poetic form, rhyme and subject matter. In the 19th century, a distinct American intonation emerged in the United States, which became a distinctive American idiom. By the end of the 20th century, when humanity would be ready for this, Walt Whitman fans in the United States became leaders of the Russian-speaking avant-garde¹. The history of American poetry is not simple. Much of the poetry written from 1910 to 1945 was lost in the pages of small periodicals such as *The New Ork Times*, which were burned by McCartney-era librarians in the 1950s.

Three monumental figures stood at the origins of American national literature. The first of them is the poet and prose writer Herman Melville, known to the general public thanks to the synthetic novel *Moby Dick*, created not according to the canons of European art, but combining several works at once, skillfully woven together. The second figure is Henry Thoreau. His book “*Walden, or Life in the Forest*”, dedicated to the experience of a two-year retreat, became the quintessence of American attitudes to the world, outlined one of the central themes of national literature - the desire to merge with nature, to return to one’s roots not with the steps of a conqueror, but with bowed head². The third was Walt Whitman. His poetry collection “*Leaves of Grass*” laid the foundation for American poetry, which took from Melville the desire to create one’s own in the meaning of the new, from Thoreau - a special, uncomplicated attitude to the world.

However, Whitman cannot be described as a combination of the features of Melville and Thoreau, his figure is much more original. It was Whitman who redirected American poetry from the path trodden by Europe, planted a new shoot in the wild, as yet unexplored soil of America. Until the advent of *Leaves of Grass*, we shall not be able to trace a significant difference in the verses written by the American and the Englishman; one can, perhaps, catch what is commonly called the difference in mentalities, but these differences do not yet concern literature proper. One of the first notable American poets was Edgar Poe, who brought back to his homeland the imagery and themes of European romanticism, bringing them as close as possible to the categories of the terrible, mysterious, and insane. But we will not yet see a purely American optics in his poems.

When referring to the work of Whitman, originality is already found at the level of form - he wrote in the so-called free verse, having previously abandoned

¹ “Walt Whitman and World Literature: Whitman in Russia,” in his: [The New Walt Whitman Handbook](#) (New York: New York University Press, 1975): 308-313.

² Henry Thoreau. *Walden, or Life in the Forest*, NY, 1910

any existing poetic forms and sizes. This form of verse should not be confused with French vers libre, on whose development Whitman's work had a significant influence: vers libre is free only by the standards of traditional versification. If the main idea of the French, to whom Whitman suggested the very possibility of a departure from the norm, was a departure from the classical laws of Alexandrian verse, then the appeal to the free verse, built on the type of biblical "verses", in Whitman's eyes, marked the birth of original American poetry.

In terms of content, Whitman's texts are also not focused on the achievements of European art. The author abandons them, planting a new type of wood grain in the soil of national literature in order to nurture it throughout life. "Leaves of Grass" is a book of books, a single volume consisting of many collections of poetry. Its composition is built linearly, and when reading, we go through the entire creative path of the poet anew - from the first poems to the last lines written in extreme old age, from "On ships in the ocean" to "Farewell, my inspiration!". In "Leaves of Grass" Whitman sings primarily about man: about his unity with nature and his compatriots, about his enthusiastic attitude towards the world, about his importance.

I celebrate myself, and sing myself,
And what I assume you shall assume,
For every atom belonging to me as good belongs to you.
I loafe and invite my soul,
I lean and loafe at my ease observing a spear of summer grass.
My tongue, every atom of my blood, form'd from this soil, this air,
Born here of parents born here from parents the same, and their parents the same,
I, now thirty-seven years old in perfect health begin,
Hoping to cease not till death.
Creeds and schools in abeyance,
Retiring back a while sufficed at what they are, but never forgotten,
I harbor for good or bad, I permit to speak at every hazard,
Nature without check with original energy³.

The lyrical hero of Whitman is extremely close to nature; studying it, he strives for synthesis, merging with it. His desire to give up worries, to find the firmness of a tree and the peace of an animal runs like a thread through the entire collection. He abandons civilization, as does Thoreau's narrator; he is characterized by dreaminess and thoughtfulness, like Melville's Ishmael. In this

³ Walt Whitman, Song of Myself, Leaves of the Grass, Brooklyn, 1855

solidarity of the subject with the natural world, one of the main lines of American poetry reveals itself - later we will turn to the work of Mary Oliver, in whose poems, after two centuries of various variations, the theme receives the most complete disclosure to date. "Leaves of Grass" from quiet but confident songs grew into a huge tree with a spreading crown. Each fruit is unique in its own way, but all of them somehow carry the sound of Whitman's songs, their biblical scope and openness to the world.

In American poetry, the natural world frequently appears. As was already established, the transcendentalist movement had a significant influence on the emergence of a distinctively American poetic voice. Transcendentalists were essentially concerned in how humans and nature interacted, as well as in rejecting the customs and comforts of contemporary civilization. The natural world has inspired American poets for generations, from Ralph Waldo Emerson through Mary Oliver.

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